

Failure of tooth supported fixed dental prosthesis and future restorability of abutment teeth among patients visiting CMH Lahore Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Extent of failure of tooth supported fixed prosthesis may affect the future restorability of abutment tooth. The objective of this study was to identify the cause of failure in tooth supported the fixed prosthesis and to assess the future restorability of abutment teeth.

Study Design: Cross sectional study.

Place and duration: Study was conducted in department of prosthodontics, Institute of Dentistry CMH Lahore Medical College in year 2016-2017.

Patients and Methods: Total 50 patients were examined with 80 abutment teeth. A self-administered Proforma was made to collect data regarding patient's age, gender, type of prosthesis and cause of failure. Intra-oral examination of patients was carried out along with prosthesis evaluation. Radiographic assessment of abutment teeth was done with the aid of peri-apical and bitewing radiographs. Failure was classified and data were analyzed using SPSS 21.

Results: Periodontal breakdown of abutment teeth was reported as a most common cause of failure (38.8%) followed by caries (31.3%), endodontic failure (7.5%), mechanical failure (6.3%), and esthetic failure (5%). Least reported factor was decementation (2%). Data showed that 32.5 % failures fall in grade 4 category, 22.1% in grade 6 followed by grade 5 (18.2%), 3 (16.9), 2 (7.8%) and 1 (2.6%) being least common.

Conclusion: While planning any fixed prosthesis the future longevity of prosthesis as well as serviceability of abutment tooth should be considered. Oral hygiene status, endodontic status and periodontal condition of abutment teeth must be assessed before giving any prosthesis.

Keywords: Fixed Partial Denture, Failure, dental abutment, Crowns, metal-ceramic crowns, complete metal crowns.

INTRODUCTION

Tooth supported fixed prosthesis are widely used to rehabilitate patients with partially lost tooth structure and missing teeth.¹ It is considered as suitable treatment option next to implants due to increased stability, retention and better affordability but like any other prosthesis, fixed prosthesis tend to fail due to a number of reasons.² Longevity of the prosthesis is of great concern for a clinician as well as the patient.³ According to Glossary of Prosthodontic Terms (GPT 9), Failure is defined as an inability of the prosthesis to produce the desired outcome. Failures of the fixed prosthesis are broadly classified into biological failure, mechanical failure and esthetic failure as listed in table I.⁴

Failure of the fixed prosthesis is usually accompanied by a need to ascertain the cause of failure and future restorability.⁵ Knowledge about the cause of failure helps the clinician in future treatment planning of patient, more realistic approach to future patients with appropriate post-treatment care instructions.^{6,7} Failure of the fixed dental prosthesis was classified into 6 grades by Manapallil as shown in Table II.⁸

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted in which patients presenting to the Department of Prosthodontics at Institute of Dentistry, CMH Lahore Medical College for removal of the fixed prosthesis were assessed. A self-administered Proforma was made to collect data regarding patient's age, gender, type of prosthesis and cause of failure. The research was conducted after approval from the ethical committee. Patients of all age group with tooth supported porcelain fused to metal, all ceramic and cast metal full coverage prosthesis were included in this study.

Intra-oral examination of patients was carried out along with prosthesis evaluation. Radiographic assessment of abutment teeth was done with the aid of peri-apical and bitewing radiographs. The condition of abutment teeth was assessed. Failure of abutment tooth was graded according to Manapallil classification given in table 2.

Data was analyzed using SPSS 21. Chi-square test was applied with a p-value of <0.5

RESULTS

Total 50 patients were examined with 80 abutment teeth out of which 16 were male and 34 female. The mean age of patients was 49 with a range of 21-76 years. The

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Table I: Causes of failure

Table II: Classification of Grade of Failure given by Manapallil⁸

Grades	Description
Grade I	Cause of failure is correctable without replacing restoration
Grade II	Cause of failure is correctable without replacing restoration; however, supporting tooth structure or foundation requires repair or reconstruction.
Grade III	Failure requiring restoration replacement only. Supporting tooth structure and/or foundation acceptable
Grade IV	Failure requiring restoration replacement in addition to repair or reconstruction of supporting tooth structure and/or foundation.
Grade V	Severe failure with loss of supporting tooth or inability to reconstruct using original tooth support. Fixed Prosthodontic replacement remains possible through the use of other or additional support for redesigned restoration.
Grade VI	Severe failure with loss of supporting tooth or inability to reconstruct using original tooth support. Conventional fixed Prosthodontic replacement is not possible.

length of survivability of prosthesis ranged from 3 months to 14 years. The incidence of causes of failure is given in Figure 1 showing that periodontal breakdown was most frequent cause accounting for 38.8% failures followed by dental caries (31%). Endodontic reasons accounted for 7.5% of failures. Loss of cementation was the least reported etiological factor (2.5%).

Data showed that 32.5 % failures fall in grade 4 category, 22.1% in grade 6 followed by grade 5 (18.2%), 3 (16.9), 2 (7.8%) and 1 (2.6%) being least common as shown in figure 2.

Figure I: Causes of failure

Figure II: Grade of failure

Table III reports an association between the cause of failure and grade of failure. It shows a greater frequency of grade 4 and grade 6 in periodontal breakdown and

caries. On the other hand cement failure, endodontic failure; biomechanical failure and esthetic failure were in grade 1, 2 and 3.

Table III: Relation between the cause of failure and grade of failure

Causes of failure	Grade of failure (frequency)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
cement failure	0	0	2	0	0	0
mechanical failure	0	0	2	0	2	0
periodontal breakdown	0	1	3	12	2	11
caries	0	1	4	5	10	5
endodontic reason	0	2	2	1	0	1
biomechanical failure	0	1	0	6	0	0
esthetic failure	0	1	0	1	0	0

DISCUSSION

The fixed dental prosthesis is considered as a definitive treatment option to restore missing tooth structure.⁹ This study is unique in surveying cause of failure and future restorability of abutment teeth. Majority of the prosthesis in our study had a survival rate of 5 years with the mean serviceability of 7 years.

In present study, periodontal breakdown of abutment teeth was reported as a most common cause of failure (38.8%). Walton et al and Ikai et al reported the incidence of periodontal problems around prostheses as 23% and 27% respectively.^{10,11} Periodontal failure is usually attributed to poor oral hygiene, host-related factors, and substandard preparation. Since periodontal breakdown is a major contributive factor towards failure it becomes

necessary to emphasize on its prevention. Any periodontal disease must be treated before giving prosthesis. The margin of preparation should be tissue friendly preventing plaque accumulation and tissue irritation⁹.

Numerous studies reported caries as the most frequent cause of failure. In our study caries is reported as a second most common etiological factor for FDP failure. The incidence of caries in our study was 31.3% similar to study conducted by de Backer. Caries is mainly attributed to marginal leakage and poor oral hygiene which can be prevented by proper case selection and adequate tooth preparation.^{4,12}

Endodontic reasons accounted for 7.5% of failures. If the

abutment tooth has doubtful endodontic status it must be treated prophylactically during stabilization phase.⁹ Many studies reported that pulpal degeneration due to iatrogenic cause occurs many years after tooth preparation. Pulpal damage may occur due to thermal injury, chemical irritation, and bacterial action. It can be prevented by following principles of tooth preparation.⁹ According to a Study conducted by Oginni poor esthetics was the most frequent cause of failure (40.5%)¹⁴ In our study failure due to esthetic reason was less common which similar to study conducted by Parwar et al (5.7%).¹⁴ Aesthetics is of major concern especially in anterior teeth thus treatment planning must focus on aesthetic expectations of the patient. Aesthetics mainly depends on operator's skill, shade selection, sub-gingival margin placement and type of fixed dental prosthesis. Least reported cause was a failure in cementation (2.5%). Oginni found cementation failure in 27.3% of the FPDs.¹³ Inadequate quality of tooth preparation (improper taper, lack of clinical crown height and improper cementation) seems to be a common thread contributing to cementation failure. Principles of tooth preparation must be emphasized to prevent loss of prosthesis.¹⁴ Ideally, the prosthesis should be made to preserve the health of abutment teeth. Failure of FDP is complex which demands a need to assess future restorability of abutment teeth. In our study majority of the failure were of Grade 4 category requiring restoration replacement in addition to repair or reconstruction of supporting tooth structure and/or foundation. 21% failures were grade 6 in which there is a loss of supporting tooth or inability to reconstruct using original tooth support. The relation between cause and grade of failure is of great concern for the clinician. In current study failure due to periodontal breakdown and caries belonged to grade 6 showing poor prognosis of abutment teeth. Abutment teeth in Esthetic failure, endodontic failure, and mechanical failure were restorable.

CONCLUSION

The success of fixed prosthesis depends on careful case selection and treatment planning to restore missing structure with preservation of biological tissues. While planning any fixed prosthesis the future longevity of prosthesis as well as serviceability of abutment tooth should be considered. Oral hygiene status, endodontic status and periodontal condition of abutment teeth must be assessed before giving any prosthesis. The dentist must plan with well-defined esthetic objectives. Regular follow-up can help in early diagnosis and prevention of abutment tooth failure.

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